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STUDIES ON INVENTORY MODEL FOR DETERIORATING ITEMS WITH WEIBULL REPLENISHMENT AND GENERALIZED PARETO DECAY HAVING SELLING PRICE DEPENDENT DEMAND

K. SrinivasaRao

Department of Statistics,
Andhra University,
Visakhapatnam, India.

A. LakshmanaRao*

Department of Basic Sciences and Humanities,
Aditya Institute of Technology and Management
Tekkali, India.

* Corresponding author

Abstract:

Inventory models play an important role in determining the optimal ordering and pricing policies. Much work has been reported in literature regarding inventory models with finite or infinite replenishment. But in many practical situations the replenishment is governed by random factors like procurement, transportation, environmental condition, availability of raw material etc., Hence, it is needed to develop inventory models with random replenishment. In this paper we develop and analyze an inventory model with the assumption that the replenishment is random and follows a Weibull distribution. It is further assumed that the life time of a commodity is random and follows a generalized Pareto distribution and demand is a function of selling price. The instantaneous level of inventory at any given time 't' is derived through differential equations. With suitable cost considerations the optimal ordering and pricing policies are obtained. The sensitivity analysis of the model reveals that the random replenishment has a significance influence on the ordering and pricing policies of the model. This model also includes some of the earlier models as particular cases for specific values of the parameters.

Keywords: Random replenishment, generalized Pareto decay, selling price demand, EPQ model, Weibull distribution.

1. INTRODUCTION

Inventory models create lot of interest due to their ready applicability at various places like market yards, ware houses, production processes, transportation systems cargo handling, etc., Several inventory models have been developed and analyzed to study various inventory systems. The most important factors influencing the inventory systems are replenishment, demand and nature of the commodity. Traditional inventory systems considered the replenishment is infinite and instantaneous these inventory models are further generalized by considering the rate of replenishment is finite and fixed. Deb, M. and Chaudhuri, [3] considered the finite rate of production. Bhunia and Maiti [1] studied two models; in one model, the production is assumed to be a function of on hand inventory level and in another the production is a function of demand rate. Billington [2] studied the EOQ model without backorders. Ouyang [7] analyzed the continuous inventory system with partial back orders. Rein Nobel [8] have considered a stochastic production inventory model with two discrete production systems. Perumal [9] introduced two rates of production in an inventory model. Sen and Chakrabarthy [11] studied an order level inventory model with variable rate of deterioration and alternative replenishment rates. In all these papers production rate is finite and fixed. But in many practical situations the production is random due to various random factors like a variability of raw

material, power supply, manpower, machine repair etc. Very little work has been reported in literature with random production except the works of Sridevi et al. [12] and Srinivas rao et al. [13]. However in these two papers they considered the rate of deterioration is constant.

But in many practical situations arising at food processing industries the life time of commodity is variable depending upon time. It is also observed that the life time of the commodity is having a finite upper bound and the rate of decay is in proportion to time. This nature can be well characterized by generalized Pareto distribution. The generalized Pareto distribution is capable representing life time of the commodity, which is having variable rate of decay. Another important factor in modeling inventory systems is the pattern of demand. It is customary to consider the demand is constant. But in some other production units dealing with food processing the demand is a function of selling price. Much work has been reported a literature regarding inventory models with selling price depend demand. Goel and Aggrawal [5], Teng, et al. [15], Srinivasa Rao and Begum [14], Maiti, et al. [6], Tripathy and Mishra [16] and Sana [10] have studied inventory models having selling price dependent demand. Essay, et al. [4] have studied inventory models with selling price dependent demand and three parameter Weibull decay having stock dependent production. Very little work has been reporting in literature regarding inventory models with random replenishment and generalized Pareto decay having selling price depended demand, which are very useful for obtaining optimal production schedules and ordering policies. Hence, in this chapter we develop and analyze an inventory model for deteriorating items with the assumption that the replenishment is random and follows a two parameter Weibull distribution. It is also assumed that life time of commodity is random and follows a generalized Pareto distribution. It is further assumed the demand is linear function of selling price. Assuming shortages are allowed and are fully back logged the instantaneous state of inventory is derived.

Using differential equations, the total cost function and profit rate function are obtained. By maximizing the profit rate function, the optimal production schedule and optimal production quantity are derived. Through numerical illustration the sensitivity analysis is carried. This model is extended to the case of without shortages. This model also includes some of the earlier models as particular cases for particular or limiting values of the parameters.

2. NOTATIONS AND ASSUMPTIONS

2.1. Notations

The following notations are used for developing the model.

Q: Ordering quantity in one cycle

A: Ordering cost

C: Cost per unit

h: Inventory holding cost per unit per unit time

π : Shortages cost per unit per unit time

s: Selling price per unit and

$\lambda(s)$: Demand rate

2.2. Assumptions

The following assumptions are made for developing the model.

i) The demand rate is a function of unit selling price which is

$$\lambda(s) = \eta - \theta s, \quad 0 < \theta < 1 \quad (1)$$

ii) The replenishment is finite and follows a two parameter Weibull distribution with probability density function $f(t) = \alpha\beta t^{\beta-1} e^{-\alpha t^\beta}$, $\alpha, \beta > 0, t > 0$

Therefore, the instantaneous rate of replenishment is

$$k(t) = \frac{f(t)}{1-F(t)} = \alpha\beta t^{\beta-1}, \quad \alpha, \beta > 0, t > 0 \quad (2)$$

iii) Lead time is zero

iv) Cycle length, T is known and fixed

v) Shortages are allowed and fully backlogged

vi) A deteriorated unit is lost

vii) The deterioration of the item is random and follows a generalized Pareto distribution. Then the instantaneous rate of deterioration is

$$h(t) = \frac{1}{a-\gamma t}, \quad 0 < t < \frac{a}{\gamma} \tag{3}$$

3. INVENTORY MODEL WITH SHORTAGES

Consider an inventory system in which the stock level is zero at time $t=0$. The Stock level increases during the period $(0, t_1)$, due to excess replenishment after fulfilling the demand and deterioration. The replenishment stops at time t_1 when the stock level reaches S . The inventory decreases gradually due to demand and deterioration in the interval (t_1, t_2) . At time t_2 the inventory reaches zero and back orders accumulate during the period (t_2, t_3) . At time t_3 the replenishment again starts and fulfils the backlog after satisfying the demand. During (t_3, T) the back orders are fulfilled and inventory level reaches zero at the end of the cycle T . The Schematic diagram representing the instantaneous state of inventory is given in Figure 1.

Fig 1: Schematic diagram representing the inventory level.

The differential equations governing the system in the cycle time $[0, T]$ are:

$$\frac{d}{dt}I(t) + h(t)I(t) = \alpha\beta t^{\beta-1} - (\eta - \theta s); \quad 0 \leq t \leq t_1 \tag{4}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}I(t) + h(t)I(t) = -(\eta - \theta s); \quad t_1 \leq t \leq t_2 \tag{5}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}I(t) = -(\eta - \theta s); \quad t_2 \leq t \leq t_3 \tag{6}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}I(t) = \alpha\beta t^{\beta-1} - (\eta - \theta s); \quad t_3 \leq t \leq T \tag{7}$$

The solution of differential equations (4) – (7) using the initial conditions, $I(0) = 0, I(t_1) = S, I(t_2) = 0$ and $I(T) = 0$, the on hand inventory at time ‘ t ’ is obtained as

$$I(t) = \left(\frac{a-\gamma t}{a-\gamma t_1}\right)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \left[S - \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\gamma - 1} (a - \gamma t_1) \right] + \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\gamma - 1} (a - \gamma t) - (a - \gamma t)^{1/\gamma} \int_t^{t_1} \alpha\beta u^{\beta-1} (a - \gamma u)^{-1/\gamma} du; \quad 0 \leq t \leq t_1 \tag{8}$$

$$I(t) = \left(\frac{a-\gamma t}{a-\gamma t_1}\right)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \left[S - \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\gamma - 1} (a - \gamma t_1) \right] + \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\gamma - 1} (a - \gamma t); \quad t_1 \leq t \leq t_2 \tag{9}$$

$$I(t) = (\eta - \theta s)(t_2 - t); \quad t_2 \leq t \leq t_3 \tag{10}$$

$$I(t) = (\eta - \theta s)(T - t) - \alpha(T^\beta - t^\beta); \quad t_3 \leq t \leq T \tag{11}$$

Stock loss due to deterioration in the interval $(0, t)$ is

$$L(t) = \int_0^t k(t)dt - \int_0^t (\eta - \theta s)dt - I(t); \quad 0 \leq t \leq t_2$$

This implies

$$L(t) = \begin{cases} \alpha t^\beta - (\eta - \theta s)t - \left\{ \left(\frac{a - \gamma t}{a - \gamma t_1} \right)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \left[S - \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\gamma - 1} (a - \gamma t_1) \right] + \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\gamma - 1} (a - \gamma t) + \right. \\ \left. (a - \gamma t)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \int_t^{t_1} (\alpha \beta u^{\beta-1}) (a - \gamma u)^{-\frac{1}{\gamma}} du \right\}; & 0 \leq t \leq t_1 \\ \alpha t_1^\beta - (\eta - \theta s)t - \left\{ \left(\frac{a - \gamma t}{a - \gamma t_1} \right)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \left[S - \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\gamma - 1} (a - \gamma t_1) \right] + \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\gamma - 1} (a - \gamma t); \right. \\ \left. \right. & t_1 \leq t \leq t_2 \end{cases}$$

Stock loss due to deterioration in the cycle of length T is

$$L(T) = \alpha t_1^\beta - (\eta - \theta s)t_2$$

Ordering quantity Q in the cycle of length T is

$$\begin{aligned} Q &= \int_0^{t_1} k(t) dt + \int_{t_3}^T k(t) dt \\ &= \alpha(t_1^\beta + T^\beta - t_3^\beta) \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

From equation (8) and using the initial conditions $I(0) = 0$, we obtain the value of 'S' as

$$S = (a - \gamma t_1)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \int_0^{t_1} \alpha \beta u^{\beta-1} (a - \gamma u)^{-\frac{1}{\gamma}} du + \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\gamma - 1} \left[(a - \gamma t_1) - a^{-\frac{1}{\gamma}+1} (a - \gamma t_1)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \right]$$

(13)

From equation (9) and using the initial condition $I(t_2) = 0$, one can get

$$t_2 = \frac{1}{\gamma} \left[a - \left(\frac{(\eta - \theta s)(a - \gamma t_2)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}}}{(\eta - \theta s)(a - \gamma t_2) - S(\gamma - 1)} \right)^{\frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma}} \right] \tag{14}$$

Substituting the value of 'S' given in equations (13) in (14), one can get t_2 in terms of t_1 as

$$t_2 = \frac{1}{\gamma} \left[a - \frac{(\eta - \theta s)^{\frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma}}}{\left((\eta - \theta s) a^{-\frac{1}{\gamma}+1} - (\gamma - 1) \int_0^{t_1} \alpha \beta u^{\beta-1} (a - \gamma u)^{-\frac{1}{\gamma}} du \right)^{\frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma}}} \right] = x(t_1, S) \text{ (say)} \tag{15}$$

when $t = t_3$, then equations (10) and (11) become

$$I(t_3) = (\eta - \theta s)(t_2 - t_3)$$

And $I(t_3) = (\eta - \theta s)(T - t_3) - \alpha(T^\beta - t_3^\beta)$ respectively

Equating the equations and on simplification, one can get

$$t_3 = \left(T^\beta - \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\alpha} (T - t_2) \right)^{1/\beta} \tag{16}$$

Substituting the value of t_2 from (15) in equation (16), one can get t_3 in terms of t_1

$$t_3 = \left(T^\beta - \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\alpha} (T - x(t_1, S)) \right)^{1/\beta}$$

$$\text{Let } y(t_1, S) = \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\alpha} (T - x(t_1, S)) \tag{17}$$

$$\text{Then } t_3 = \left(T^\beta - y(t_1, s)\right)^{1/\beta} \tag{18}$$

Let $K(t_1, t_2, t_3, s)$ be the total cost per unit time. Since the total cost is the sum of the set up cost, cost of the units, the inventory holding cost, the total cost per unit time becomes

$$K(t_1, t_2, t_3, s) = \frac{A}{T} + \frac{CQ}{T} + \frac{h}{T} \left(\int_0^{t_1} I(t) dt + \int_{t_1}^{t_2} I(t) dt \right) + \frac{\pi}{T} \left(\int_{t_2}^{t_3} -I(t) dt + \int_{t_3}^T -I(t) dt \right) \tag{19}$$

Substituting the values of $I(t)$ and Q in equation (19) and on simplification one can obtain $K(t_1, t_2, t_3, s)$ as

$$\begin{aligned} K(t_1, t_2, t_3, s) &= \frac{A}{T} + \frac{C}{T} \alpha (t_1^\beta + T^\beta - t_3^\beta) \\ &+ \frac{h}{T} \left\{ - \int_0^{t_1} \left[(a - \gamma t)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \left[\int_t^{t_1} \alpha \beta u^{\beta-1} (a - \gamma u)^{-\frac{1}{\gamma}} du \right] \right] dt \right. \\ &+ \frac{s}{\gamma + 1} \left[\frac{a^{\frac{1}{\gamma}+1}}{(a - \gamma t_1)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}}} - \frac{(a - \gamma t_2)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}}}{(a - \gamma t_1)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}}} (a - \gamma t_2) \right] \\ &+ \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{(\gamma - 1)(\gamma + 1)} \left[(a - \gamma t_1)^{-\frac{1}{\gamma}+1} (a - \gamma t_2)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}+1} - \frac{a^{\frac{1}{\gamma}+1} (a - \gamma t_1)}{(a - \gamma t_1)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}}} \right] \\ &+ \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\gamma - 1} \left[a t_2 - \frac{\gamma t_2^2}{2} \right] + \frac{\pi}{T} \left\{ \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{2} [(t_2^2 - t^2) + 2 t_3 (T - t_2)] \right. \\ &\left. + \alpha \left(\beta \frac{T^{\beta+1}}{\beta+1} - T^\beta t_3 + \frac{t_3^{\beta+1}}{\beta+1} \right) \right\} \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

Let $P(t_1, t_2, t_3, s)$ be the profit rate function. Since the profit rate function is the total revenue per unit minus total cost per unit time, we have

$$P(t_1, t_2, t_3, s) = s (\eta - \theta s) - K(t_1, t_2, t_3, s) \tag{21}$$

Substituting the equations (13), (15), (18) and (20) in equation (21), one can get the profit rate function in terms of 't₁' and 's' as

$$\begin{aligned} P(t_1, s) &= s (\eta - \theta s) - \frac{A}{T} - \frac{C}{T} \alpha (t_1^\beta + T^\beta - t_3^\beta) \\ &- \frac{h}{T} \left\{ - \int_0^{t_1} \left[(a - \gamma t)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \left[\int_t^{t_1} \alpha \beta u^{\beta-1} (a - \gamma u)^{-\frac{1}{\gamma}} du \right] \right] dt \right. \\ &+ \frac{1}{\gamma + 1} \left[\left[a^{\frac{1}{\gamma}+1} - (a - \gamma x(t_1, s))^{\frac{1}{\gamma}+1} \right] \int_0^{t_1} \alpha \beta u^{\beta-1} (a - \gamma t)^{-\frac{1}{\gamma}} du \right] \\ &+ \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{(\gamma - 1)(\gamma + 1)} \left[a^{-\frac{1}{\gamma}+1} (a - \gamma x(t_1, s))^{\frac{1}{\gamma}+1} - a^2 \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\gamma - 1} \left[ax(t_1, s) - \frac{\gamma(x(t_1, s))^2}{2} \right] \\
 & - \frac{\pi}{T} \left\{ \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{2} \left[((x(t_1, s))^2 - T^2) + 2(T^\beta - y(t_1, s))^{1/\beta} (T - x(t_1, s)) \right] \right. \\
 & \left. + \alpha \beta \frac{T^{\beta+1}}{\beta+1} - T^\beta (T^\beta - y(t_1, s))^{1/\beta} + \frac{1}{\beta+1} \left[(T^\beta - y(t_1, s))^{\beta/\beta+1} \right] \right\} \tag{22}
 \end{aligned}$$

4. OPTIMAL PRICING AND ORDERING POLICIES OF THE MODEL

In this section we obtain the optimal policies of the inventory system under study. To find the optimal values of t_1 and s , we obtain the first order partial derivatives of $P(t_1, s)$ given in equation (22) with respect to t_1 and s and equate them to zero. The condition for maximization of $P(t_1, s)$ is

$$D = \begin{vmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 P(t_1, s)}{\partial t_1^2} & \frac{\partial^2 P(t_1, s)}{\partial t_1 \partial s} \\ \frac{\partial^2 P(t_1, s)}{\partial t_1 \partial s} & \frac{\partial^2 P(t_1, s)}{\partial s^2} \end{vmatrix} < 0$$

Using equation (15), one can get

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial z_1}{\partial t_1} &= \frac{\partial x(t_1, s)}{\partial t_1} \\
 \text{Let } z_1(t_1, s) &= \frac{\partial x(t_1, s)}{\partial t_1} \tag{23}
 \end{aligned}$$

From equations (15) and (23), one can get

$$\begin{aligned}
 z_1(t_1, s) &= (\eta - \theta s)^{\frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma}} \alpha \beta t_1^{\beta-1} (a - \gamma t_1)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \\
 & \left[\left((\gamma - 1) \int_0^{t_1} \alpha \beta u^{\beta-1} (a - \gamma u)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} du - (\eta - \theta s) a^{\frac{1}{\gamma+1}} \right)^{\frac{1}{\gamma-1}} \right] \tag{24}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Let } z_2(t_1, s) = \frac{\partial x(t_1, s)}{\partial s} \tag{25}$$

Using equation (15), equation (25) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 z_2(t_1, s) &= \frac{\theta}{\gamma-1} \left[a^{\frac{1}{\gamma}+1} (\eta - \theta s)^{\frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma}} \left((\eta - \theta s) a^{\frac{1}{\gamma}+1} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. - (\gamma - 1) \int_0^{t_1} \alpha \beta u^{\beta-1} (a - \gamma u)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} du \right)^{\frac{1}{\gamma-1}} \right. \\
 & \left. - (\eta - \theta s)^{\frac{1-2\gamma}{\gamma-1}} \left((\eta - \theta s) a^{\frac{1}{\gamma}+1} - (\gamma - 1) \int_0^{t_1} \alpha \beta u^{\beta-1} (a - \gamma u)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} du \right)^{\frac{\gamma}{1-\gamma}} \right] \tag{26}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Let } z_3(t_1, s) = \frac{\partial y(t_1, s)}{\partial s} \tag{27}$$

where, $y(t_1, s)$ is as given in equation (17)

Using equations (17) and (27), $z_3(t_1, s)$ can be written as

$$z_3(t_1, s) = (T - x(t_1, s)) \frac{(-\theta)}{\alpha} - \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\alpha} (z_2(t_1, s)) \tag{28}$$

Differentiate $P(t_1, s)$ given in equation (22) with respect to t_1 , using equations (17) and (24) and equating to zero, one can get

$$\begin{aligned} & C \left((\eta - \theta s) z_1(t_1, s) - \alpha \beta t_1^{\beta-1} \right) \\ & + h \left\{ \frac{\alpha \beta t_1^{\beta-1} (a - \gamma t_1)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}}}{(\gamma + 1)} \left[(a - \gamma t_1)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}+1} - (a - \gamma x(t_1, s))^{\frac{1}{\gamma}+1} \right] \right. \\ & + \left[(a - \gamma x(t_1, s))^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} (z_1(t_1, s)) \int_0^{t_1} \alpha \beta u^{\beta-1} (a - \gamma u)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} du \right] \\ & + \left. \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\gamma - 1} z_1(t_1, s) \left[a - a^{\frac{1}{\gamma}+1} (a - \gamma x(t_1, s))^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} - \gamma x(t_1, s) \right] \right\} \\ & + \pi (\eta - \theta s) z_1(t_1, s) \left\{ x(t_1, s) + (T^\beta - y(t_1, s))^{\frac{1}{\beta}-1} \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\alpha \beta} (T - x(t_1, s)) \right. \\ & \left. - T^\beta + y(t_1, s) - \frac{y(t_1, s)}{\beta} \right\} = 0 \end{aligned} \tag{29}$$

Differentiating $P(t_1, s)$ given in equation (22) with respect to 's', using equations (26) and (28) and equating to zero, one can get

$$\begin{aligned} & T(2s\theta - \eta) + C \alpha z_3(t_1, s) \\ & + h \left\{ -z_2(t_1, s) (a - \gamma x(t_1, s))^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \int_0^{t_1} \alpha \beta u^{\beta-1} (a - \gamma u)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} du \right. \\ & + \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\gamma - 1} z_2(t_1, s) \left[a - \gamma x(t_1, s) - a^{\frac{1}{\gamma}+1} (a - \gamma x(t_1, s))^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \right] \\ & - \frac{\theta}{(\gamma - 1)(\gamma + 1)} \left(a^{-\frac{1}{\gamma}+1} (a - \gamma x(t_1, s))^{\frac{1}{\gamma}+1} - a^2 \right) - \frac{\theta}{(\gamma - 1)} \left(ax(t_1, s) + \gamma \frac{(x(t_1, s))^2}{2} \right) \\ & + \pi \left\{ (\eta - \theta s) \left[x(t_1, s) (z_2(t_1, s)) - (T^\beta - y(t_1, s))^{\frac{1}{\beta}-1} \left[(T^\beta - y(t_1, s))^{\frac{1}{\beta}} z_2(t_1, s) \right. \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. + \frac{z_3(t_1, s) (T - x(t_1, s))}{\beta} \right] \right\} - \frac{\theta}{2} \left[2 (T^\beta - y(t_1, s))^{\frac{1}{\beta}} (T - x(t_1, s)) + (x(t_1, s))^2 - T^2 \right] \\ & \left. + \frac{\alpha z_3(t_1, s)}{\beta} \left[(T^\beta - y(t_1, s))^{\frac{1}{\beta}-1} y(t_1, s) \right] \right\} = 0 \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

Solving the equations (29) and (30) simultaneously, we obtain the optimal time at which replenishment is stopped t_1^* of t_1 and the optimal selling price s^* of s . The optimal time t_3^* of t_3 at which the replenishment is restarted is obtained by substituting the optimal values of t_1 and s in equation (18). The optimum ordering quantity Q^* of Q in the cycle of length T is obtained by substituting the optimal values of t_1^* , t_3^* and s^* in equation (12).

5. NUMERICAL ILLUSTRATIONS

In this section we discuss the solution procedure of the model through a numerical illustration by obtaining the replenishment (production) uptime, replenishment (production) down time, optimal selling price, optimal quantity and profit of an inventory system. Here, it is assumed that the commodity is of deteriorating nature and shortages are allowed and fully back logged. The following parameter values: $A = \text{Rs.}200/-$ $C = \text{Rs.}10/-$ $h = \text{Rs.} 2/-$ $\pi = \text{Rs.} 3/-$ $T = 12$ months. For the assigned values of replenishment parameters $(\alpha, \beta) = (20, 0.4)$, deterioration parameters $(a, \gamma) = (10, 0.02)$ and demand parameters $(\eta, \theta) = (12, 0.2)$. The values of above parameters are varied further to observe the trend in optimal policies and the results obtained are shown in Table1. Substituting these values the optimal ordering quantity Q^* , replenishment uptime, replenishment down time, optimal selling price and total profit are computed and presented in Table 1.

From Table 1 it is observed that the deterioration parameter and replenishment parameters have a tremendous influence on the optimal values of replenishment times, ordering quantity and profit rate function.

If the ordering cost ‘A’ increases from 200 to 230, then the optimal replenishment down time t_1^* decreases from 4.50 to 4.46, the optimal replenishment uptime t_3^* decreases from 9.43 to 9.40, the optimal selling price s^* decreases from 45.51 to 45.31, the optimal ordering quantity Q^* decreases from 41.46 to 41.42, the total profit P^* decreases from 64.66 to 63.73. The cost parameter C increases from 10 to 11.5, the optimal replenishment down time decreases from 4.50 to 4.32, the optimal replenishment uptime decreases from 9.43 to 8.71, the optimal selling price decreases from 45.51 to 45.11, the optimal ordering quantity Q^* increases from 41.46 to 42.43 and the total profit decreases from 64.66 to 61.97.

Table 1
Optimal values of t_1^* , t_3^* , s^* , Q^* and P^* for different values of parameters

A	C	h	π	T	α	β	γ	a	η	θ	t_1	t_3	S	Q	P
200	10	2	3	12	20	0.4	0.02	10	12	0.2	4.50	9.43	45.51	41.46	64.66
210	10	2	3	12	20	0.4	0.02	10	12	0.2	4.49	9.42	45.44	41.45	64.34
220	10	2	3	12	20	0.4	0.02	10	12	0.2	4.47	9.41	45.38	41.43	64.04
230	10	2	3	12	20	0.4	0.02	10	12	0.2	4.46	9.40	45.31	41.42	63.73
200	10.5	2	3	12	20	0.4	0.02	10	12	0.2	4.43	9.19	45.38	41.76	63.75
200	11.0	2	3	12	20	0.4	0.02	10	12	0.2	4.38	8.94	45.25	42.09	62.85
200	11.5	2	3	12	20	0.4	0.02	10	12	0.2	4.32	8.71	45.11	42.43	61.97
200	10	2.1	3	12	20	0.4	0.02	10	12	0.2	4.50	9.31	45.30	41.72	65.22
200	10	2.2	3	12	20	0.4	0.02	10	12	0.2	4.50	9.19	45.10	41.96	65.72
200	10	2.3	3	12	20	0.4	0.02	10	12	0.2	4.49	9.07	44.91	42.18	66.17
200	10	2	3.15	12	20	0.4	0.02	10	12	0.2	4.60	9.64	45.45	41.35	65.01
200	10	2	3.30	12	20	0.4	0.02	10	12	0.2	4.70	9.83	45.37	41.29	65.41
200	10	2	3.45	12	20	0.4	0.02	10	12	0.2	4.81	10.0	45.29	41.28	65.83
200	10	2	3	12	21	0.4	0.02	10	12	0.2	4.29	9.50	45.46	41.35	62.68
200	10	2	3	12	22	0.4	0.02	10	12	0.2	4.10	9.58	45.42	41.29	60.77
200	10	2	3	12	23	0.4	0.02	10	12	0.2	3.92	9.67	45.39	41.28	58.91
200	10	2	3	12	20	0.42	0.02	10	12	0.2	4.26	9.22	45.47	42.73	63.18
200	10	2	3	12	20	0.44	0.02	10	12	0.2	4.04	9.02	45.43	44.04	61.76
200	10	2	3	12	20	0.46	0.02	10	12	0.2	3.83	8.83	45.39	45.36	60.39
200	10	2	3	12	20	0.4	0.03	10	12	0.2	4.51	9.43	45.51	41.46	64.64
200	10	2	3	12	20	0.4	0.04	10	12	0.2	4.52	9.44	45.52	41.47	64.63
200	10	2	3	12	20	0.4	0.05	10	12	0.2	4.52	9.44	45.52	41.47	64.61
200	10	2	3	12	20	0.4	0.02	10.5	12	0.2	4.49	9.45	45.47	41.40	64.62
200	10	2	3	12	20	0.4	0.02	11.0	12	0.2	4.49	9.47	45.43	41.35	64.59
200	10	2	3	12	20	0.4	0.02	11.5	12	0.2	4.48	9.49	45.39	41.30	64.56
200	10	2	3	12	20	0.4	0.02	10	12.3	0.2	4.30	9.68	47.56	40.66	67.44
200	10	2	3	12	20	0.4	0.02	10	12.6	0.2	4.10	9.98	50.03	39.02	67.75
200	10	2	3	12	20	0.4	0.02	10	12.9	0.2	3.72	10.3	53.29	38.17	71.60
200	10	2	3	12	20	0.4	0.02	10	12	0.21	4.60	9.16	42.67	42.35	63.97
200	10	2	3	12	20	0.4	0.02	10	12	0.22	4.60	9.04	40.18	42.28	60.93
200	10	2	3	12	20	0.4	0.02	10	12	0.23	4.37	8.93	38.17	42.12	57.72

As the inventory holding cost 'h' increases from 2 to 2.3, then the optimal replenishment down time t_1^* decreases from 4.50 to 4.49, the replenishment uptime t_3^* decreases from 9.43 to 9.07, the selling price decreases from 45.51 to 44.91 the optimal ordering quantity increases from 41.46 to 42.18 and the total profit increases from 64.66 to 66.17. As the shortage cost ' π ' increases from 3 to 3.45, the optimal replenishment down time increases from 4.50 to 4.81, the optimal replenishment uptime increases from 9.43 to 10.05, the optimal selling price decreases from 45.51 to 45.29, the optimal ordering quantity decreases from 41.46 to 41.28 and total profit increases from 64.66 to 65.83.

As the replenishment parameter ' α ' increases from 20 to 23 units, the optimal replenishment down time decreases from 4.50 to 3.92, the optimal replenishment uptime increases from 9.43 to 9.67, the optimal selling price decreases from 45.51 to 45.39, the optimal ordering quantity Q^* decreases from 41.46 to 41.28 and the total profit decreases from 64.66 to 58.91. The replenishment parameter ' β ' increases from 0.4 to 0.46, the optimal value of t_1^* decreases from 4.50 to 3.83, the optimal value of t_3^* decreases from 9.43 to 8.83, the optimal selling price s^* decreases from 45.51 to 45.39, the optimal ordering quantity Q^* increases from 41.46 to 45.36, the total profit P^* decreases from 64.66 to 60.39.

As the deteriorating parameter ' γ ' varies from 0.02 to 0.05, the optimal replenishment down time increases from 4.50 to 4.52, the optimal replenishment uptime increases from 9.43 to 9.44, the optimal selling price increases from 45.51 to 45.52, the optimal ordering quantity Q^* increases from 41.46 to 41.47, the total profit decreases from 64.66 to 64.61. Another deteriorating parameter ' α ' increases from 10 to 11.5, the optimal replenishment down time decreases from 4.50 to 4.48, the optimal replenishment uptime increases from 9.43 to 9.49, the optimal selling price decreases from 45.51 to 45.39, the optimal ordering quantity decreases from 41.46 to 41.30, the total profit decreases from 64.66 to 64.56.

The demand parameter ' η ' increases from 12 to 12.9 the optimal value of t_1^* decreases from 4.50 to 3.52, the optimal value of t_3^* increases from 9.43 to 10.30, the optimal value of s^* increases from 45.51 to 53.29, the optimal value of Q^* decreases from 41.46 to 36.27, the total profit P^* increases from 64.66 to 71.60. Another demand parameter ' θ ' increases from 0.2 to 0.23, the optimal replenishment down time increases from 4.50 to 4.71, the optimal replenishment uptime decreases from 9.43 to 8.93, the optimal selling price decreases from 45.51 to 38.17, the optimal order quantity increases from 41.46 to 42.12, the total profit decreases from 64.66 to 57.72.

6. SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS OF THE MODEL

The sensitivity analysis is carried to explore the effect of changes in model parameters and costs on the optimal policies, by varying each parameter (-15%, -10%, -5%, 0%, 5%, 10%, 15%) at a time for the model under study. The results are presented in Table 2. The relationship between the parameters and the optimal values are shown in Figure 2.

It is observed that the costs are having significant influence on the optimal ordering quantity and replenishment schedules. As the ordering cost A decreases, the optimal replenishment down time t_1^* , the optimal replenishment uptime t_3^* , optimal selling price s^* , the optimal ordering quantity Q^* and total profit P^* are increasing. As ordering cost A increases, the optimal replenishment down time t_1^* , the optimal replenishment uptime t_3^* , the optimal selling price s^* , the optimal ordering quantity Q^* and total profit P^* are decreasing. As the cost per unit C decreases, the optimal replenishment uptime t_3^* , the optimal replenishment down time t_1^* , optimal selling price s^* and total profit P^* are increasing and the optimal ordering quantity Q^* decreases. As the cost per unit C increases, the optimal replenishment uptime t_3^* , the optimal replenishment down time t_1^* , optimal selling price s^* and total profit P^* are decreasing and the optimal ordering quantity Q^* increases.

As the holding cost 'h' decreases, the optimal values of t_1^* , Q^* and P^* are decreasing and the optimal values of t_3^* , s^* are increasing. As the holding cost 'h' increases, the optimal values of t_1^* , t_3^* , s^* are decreasing and the optimal ordering quantity Q^* , optimal profit P^* are increasing. As the penalty cost ' π ' decreases, the optimal replenishment uptime t_3^* , the optimal replenishment down time t_1^* and

the total profit P^* are decreasing and the optimal selling price s^* , the optimal ordering quantity Q^* are increasing. As the penalty cost π increases, the optimal replenishment uptime t_3^* , the optimal replenishment down time t_1^* and the total profit P^* are increasing and the optimal selling price s^* , the optimal ordering quantity Q^* are decreasing.

As the replenishment parameter ' α ' decreases, the optimal values of t_1^* , s^* and P^* are increasing, the optimal value of t_3^* , Q^* are decreasing. As ' α ' increases, the optimal values of t_1^* , s^* and P^* are decreasing and the optimal value of t_3^* , Q^* are increasing. Another replenishment parameter ' β ' decreases, the optimal values of t_1^* , t_3^* , s^* and P^* are increasing and the optimal ordering quantity Q^* decreases. As ' β ' increases, the optimal values of t_1^* , t_3^* , s^* and P^* are decreasing and the optimal ordering quantity Q^* increases.

Table 2
Sensitivity analysis of the model - with shortages

Variation Parameters	Optimal Policies	Change in parameters						
		-15%	-10%	-5%	0%	5%	10%	15%
A	t_1^*	4.531	4.521	4.51	4.5	4.49	4.479	4.469
	t_3^*	9.464	9.453	9.443	9.433	9.423	9.413	9.404
	s^*	45.702	45.639	45.575	45.511	45.447	45.383	45.319
	Q^*	41.496	41.486	41.475	41.463	41.45	41.436	41.421
	P^*	65.597	65.283	64.971	64.66	64.349	64.04	63.731
C	t_1^*	4.708	4.636	4.566	4.5	4.438	4.38	4.326
	t_3^*	10.146	9.912	9.674	9.433	9.19	8.949	8.71
	s^*	45.841	45.737	45.628	45.511	45.388	45.257	45.118
	Q^*	40.678	40.917	41.179	41.463	41.768	42.092	42.431
	P^*	67.445	66.507	65.578	64.66	63.752	62.857	61.974
h	t_1^*	4.44	4.47	4.489	4.5	4.504	4.501	4.494
	t_3^*	9.79	9.67	9.551	9.433	9.315	9.197	9.078
	s^*	46.245	45.982	45.738	45.511	45.3	45.101	44.914
	Q^*	40.533	40.875	41.183	41.463	41.721	41.961	42.187
	P^*	62.476	63.298	64.021	64.66	65.225	65.728	66.177
π	t_1^*	4.235	4.314	4.403	4.5	4.602	4.708	4.814
	t_3^*	8.724	8.97	9.207	9.433	9.643	9.835	10.005
	s^*	45.58	45.582	45.557	45.511	45.45	45.377	45.296
	Q^*	42.097	41.828	41.619	41.463	41.357	41.299	41.289
	P^*	64.15	64.196	64.378	64.66	65.012	65.411	65.838
α	t_1^*	5.24	4.968	4.724	4.5	4.294	4.102	3.921
	t_3^*	9.315	9.33	9.372	9.433	9.505	9.586	9.671
	s^*	45.669	45.613	45.56	45.511	45.467	45.427	45.394
	Q^*	42.097	41.828	41.619	41.463	41.357	41.299	41.289
	P^*	71.033	68.83	66.706	64.66	62.684	60.771	58.913
β	t_1^*	5.279	5.003	4.744	4.5	4.269	4.049	3.838
	t_3^*	10.147	9.891	9.655	9.433	9.223	9.024	8.836
	s^*	45.625	45.588	45.55	45.511	45.473	45.434	45.397
	Q^*	37.792	38.994	40.216	41.463	42.738	44.04	45.368
	P^*	69.578	67.839	66.206	64.66	63.184	61.767	60.399
a	t_1^*	4.515	4.51	4.505	4.5	4.496	4.492	4.488
	t_3^*	9.362	9.387	9.411	9.433	9.453	9.473	9.491
	s^*	45.655	45.603	45.555	45.511	45.471	45.433	45.398
	Q^*	41.658	41.589	41.524	41.463	41.406	41.352	41.301
	P^*	64.741	64.716	64.689	64.66	64.629	64.597	64.565
η	t_1^*	5.48	5.15	4.67	4.5	4.301	4.109	3.721
	t_3^*	8.32	8.743	9.128	9.433	9.684	9.985	10.308
	s^*	39.081	40.752	43.055	45.511	47.567	50.038	53.291
	Q^*	42.996	42.597	41.959	41.463	40.661	39.029	38.178
	P^*	51.902	56.238	60.367	64.66	67.445	69.757	71.603
θ	t_1^*	3.5	3.868	4.18	4.5	4.603	4.603	4.71
	t_3^*	9.882	9.765	9.668	9.433	9.166	9.046	8.933
	s^*	53.316	51.52	48.572	45.511	42.671	40.185	38.179
	Q^*	36.796	36.395	40.251	41.463	42.355	42.28	42.12
	P^*	40.186	50.012	58.647	64.66	63.97	60.93	57.721

The deteriorating parameter 'a' decreases, the optimal values of t_1^* , s^* , Q^* and P^* are increasing, the optimal replenishment uptime t_3^* decreases. As 'a' increases, the optimal values of t_1^* , s^* , Q^* and P^* are decreasing, the optimal replenishment uptime t_3^* increases.

The demand parameter 'η' decreases, the optimal values of t_3^* , s^* and P^* are decreasing, the optimal values of t_1^* and Q^* increases. As parameter 'η' increases, the optimal values of t_1^* , Q^* and P^* are decreasing and the optimal values of t_3^* , s^* are increasing. As the demand parameter 'θ' decreases, the optimal values of t_1^* , s^* , Q^* and P^* are decreasing, the optimal value of t_3^* increases. As the parameter 'θ' increases, the optimal values of t_3^* , s^* and P^* are decreasing, the optimal value of t_1^* , Q^* are increasing.

Fig 2: Relationship between parameters and optimal values with shortages

7. INVENTORY MODEL WITHOUT SHORTAGES

In this section the inventory model for deteriorating items without shortages is developed and analyzed. Here, it is assumed that shortages are not allowed and the stock level is zero at time $t = 0$.

The stock level increases during the period (0, t₁) due to excess replenishment after fulfilling the demand and deterioration. The replenishment stops at time t₁ when the stock level reaches S. The inventory decreases gradually due to demand and deterioration in the interval (t₁, T). At time T the inventory reaches zero. The Schematic diagram representing the instantaneous state of inventory is given in Figure 3

Fig 3: Schematic diagram representing the inventory level.

The differential equations governing the system in the cycle time [0, T] are:

$$\frac{d}{dt}I(t) + h(t)I(t) = \alpha\beta t^{\beta-1} - (\eta - \theta s), \quad 0 \leq t \leq t_1 \tag{31}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}I(t) + h(t)I(t) = -(\eta - \theta s), \quad t_1 \leq t \leq T \tag{32}$$

The solution of differential equations (31) and (32) using the initial conditions, I(0) = 0, I(t₁) = S, and I(T) = 0, the on hand inventory at time 't' is obtained as

$$I(t) = \left(\frac{a - \gamma t}{a - \gamma t_1}\right)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \left[S - \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\gamma - 1} (a - \gamma t_1) \right] + \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\gamma - 1} (a - \gamma t) - (a - \gamma t)^{1/\gamma} \int_t^{t_1} \alpha\beta u^{\beta-1} (a - \gamma u)^{-1/\gamma} du, \quad 0 \leq t \leq t_1 \tag{33}$$

$$I(t) = \left(\frac{a - \gamma t}{a - \gamma t_1}\right)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \left[S - \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\gamma - 1} (a - \gamma t_1) \right] + \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\gamma - 1} (a - \gamma t), \quad t_1 \leq t \leq T \tag{34}$$

Stock loss due to deterioration in the interval (0, t) is

$$L(t) = \int_0^t k(t)dt - \int_0^t (\eta - \theta s)dt - I(t), \quad 0 \leq t \leq T$$

This implies

$$L(t) = \begin{cases} at^\beta - (\eta - \theta s)t - \left\{ \left(\frac{a - \gamma t}{a - \gamma t_1}\right)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \left[S - \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\gamma - 1} (a - \gamma t_1) \right] + \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\gamma - 1} (a - \gamma t) + (a - \gamma t)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \int_t^{t_1} (\alpha\beta u^{\beta-1}) (a - \gamma u)^{-\frac{1}{\gamma}} du \right\}; & 0 \leq t \leq t_1 \\ at_1^\beta - (\eta - \theta s)t - \left\{ \left(\frac{a - \gamma t}{a - \gamma t_1}\right)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \left[S - \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\gamma - 1} (a - \gamma t_1) \right] + \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\gamma - 1} (a - \gamma t); \right. & t_1 \leq t \leq T \end{cases}$$

Ordering quantity Q in the cycle of length T is

$$Q = \int_0^{t_1} k(t)dt = \alpha t_1^\beta \tag{35}$$

From equation (33) and using the initial conditions I(0) = 0, we obtain the value of 'S' as

$$S = (a - \gamma t_1)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \int_0^{t_1} \alpha \beta u^{\beta-1} (a - \gamma u)^{-1/\gamma} du + \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\gamma - 1} \left[(a - \gamma t_1) - a^{-\frac{1}{\gamma}+1} (a - \gamma t_1)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \right] \tag{36}$$

Let $K(t_1, s)$ be the total cost per unit time. Since the total cost is the sum of the set up cost, cost of the units, the inventory holding cost. Therefore the total cost is

$$K(t_1, s) = \frac{A}{T} + \frac{CQ}{T} + \frac{h}{T} \left(\int_0^{t_1} I(t) dt + \int_{t_1}^T I(t) dt \right) \tag{37}$$

Substituting the value of I (t) and Q given in equation's (33), (34) and (35) in equation (37) and on simplification, we obtain $K(t_1, s)$ as

$$\begin{aligned} K(t_1, s) = & \frac{A}{T} + \frac{C}{T} \alpha t_1^\beta + \frac{h}{T} \left\{ - \int_0^{t_1} \left[(a - \gamma t)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \left[\int_t^{t_1} \alpha \beta u^{\beta-1} (a - \gamma t)^{\frac{-1}{\gamma}} du \right] \right] dt \right. \\ & + \frac{S}{\gamma + 1} \left[\frac{a^{\frac{1}{\gamma}+1}}{(a - \gamma t_1)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}}} - \frac{(a - \gamma T)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}}}{(a - \gamma t_1)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}}} (a - \gamma T) \right] \\ & \left. + \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{(\gamma - 1)(\gamma + 1)} \left[(a - \gamma t_1)^{-\frac{1}{\gamma}+1} (a - \gamma T)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}+1} - \frac{a^{\frac{1}{\gamma}+1} (a - \gamma t_1)}{(a - \gamma t_1)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}}} \right] + \frac{(\eta - \theta s)}{\gamma - 1} \left[aT - \frac{\gamma T^2}{2} \right] \right\} \tag{38} \end{aligned}$$

Let $P(t_1, s)$ be the profit rate function. Since the profit rate function is the total revenue per unit minus total cost per unit time, we have

$$P(t_1, s) = s(\eta - \theta s) - K(t_1, s) \tag{39}$$

where, $K(t_1, s)$ is as defined in (38)

8. OPTIMAL PRICING AND ORDERING POLICIES OF THE MODEL

In this section we obtain the optimal policies of the inventory system under study. To find the optimal values of t_1 and s , we equate the first order partial derivatives of $P(t_1, s)$ with respect to t_1 and s equates them to zero. The condition for maximization of $P(t_1, s)$ is

$$D = \begin{vmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 P(t_1, s)}{\partial t_1^2} & \frac{\partial^2 P(t_1, s)}{\partial t_1 \partial s} \\ \frac{\partial^2 P(t_1, s)}{\partial t_1 \partial s} & \frac{\partial^2 P(t_1, s)}{\partial s^2} \end{vmatrix} < 0$$

Differentiate $P(t_1, s)$ with respect to t_1 and equating to zero, one can get

$$\begin{aligned} & C \alpha \beta t_1^{\beta-1} + h \left\{ - \frac{\partial}{\partial t_1} \left[\int_0^{t_1} \left[(a - \gamma t)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \left[\int_t^{t_1} \alpha \beta u^{\beta-1} (a - \gamma t)^{\frac{-1}{\gamma}} du \right] \right] dt \right\} \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{1}{\gamma + 1} \left[(a^{\frac{1}{\gamma}+1} - (a - \gamma T)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}+1}) \alpha \beta t_1^{\beta-1} (a - \gamma t_1)^{\frac{-1}{\gamma}} \right] \right\} = 0 \tag{40} \end{aligned}$$

Differentiate $P(t_1, s)$ with respect to 's' and equating to zero, one can get

$$T(2s\theta - \eta) + h \left\{ \frac{\theta}{\gamma-1} \left[\frac{a^{-\frac{1}{\gamma}+1}(a-\gamma T)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}+1} - a^2}{\gamma+1} + \left[aT - \frac{\gamma T^2}{2} \right] \right] \right\} = 0 \tag{41}$$

Solving the equations (40) and (41) simultaneously, we obtain the optimal time at which the replenishment is to be stopped t_1^* of t_1 and the optimal unit selling price s^* of s . The optimum ordering quantity Q^* of Q in the cycle of length T is obtained by substituting the optimal values of t_1 in (35).

9. NUMERICAL ILLUSTRATIONS

In this section, we discuss a numerical illustration of the model. For demonstrating the solution procedure of the model, let the inventory system without shortages has the following parameter values: $A = \text{Rs.}1000/-$ $C = \text{Rs.}10/-$ $h = \text{Rs.}0.2/-$ $T = 12$ months. For the assigned values of replenishment parameters $(\alpha, \beta) = (12, 3)$, deterioration parameters $(a, \gamma) = (10, 12)$ and demand parameters $(\eta, \theta) = (12, 0.2)$. The values of above parameters are varied further to observe the trend in optimal policies and the results obtained are shown in Table3. Substituting these values the optimal ordering quantity Q^* , replenishment time, optimal selling price and optimal profit per unit time are computed and presented in Table 3.

Table 3
Optimal values of t_1^* , s^* , Q^* and P^* for different values of parameters

A	C	h	T	α	β	γ	a	η	θ	t_1	s	Q	P
1000	10	0.2	12	12	3	2	10	12	0.2	1.57	33.26	46.63	58.80
1050	10	0.2	12	12	3	2	10	12	0.2	1.55	34.03	45.36	54.47
1100	10	0.2	12	12	3	2	10	12	0.2	1.53	34.99	43.76	49.78
1150	10	0.2	12	12	3	2	10	12	0.2	1.52	35.70	42.58	44.99
1000	10.5	0.2	12	12	3	2	10	12	0.2	1.58	33.43	46.34	56.76
1000	11.0	0.2	12	12	3	2	10	12	0.2	1.56	33.53	46.19	54.9
1000	11.5	0.2	12	12	3	2	10	12	0.2	1.54	34.85	43.99	52.71
1000	10	0.21	12	12	3	2	10	12	0.2	1.57	33.21	46.58	58.95
1000	10	0.22	12	12	3	2	10	12	0.2	1.59	32.27	48.26	58.98
1000	10	0.23	12	12	3	2	10	12	0.2	1.59	32.26	48.88	59.14
1000	10	0.2	12	12.6	3	2	10	12	0.2	1.56	33.35	46.43	58.53
1000	10	0.2	12	13.2	3	2	10	12	0.2	1.51	33.72	46.19	58.52
1000	10	0.2	12	13.8	3	2	10	12	0.2	1.49	33.74	46.15	58.42
1000	10	0.2	12	12	3.15	2	10	12	0.2	1.53	33.30	46.63	58.72
1000	10	0.2	12	12	3.30	2	10	12	0.2	1.50	33.34	46.63	58.66
1000	10	0.2	12	12	3.45	2	10	12	0.2	1.48	33.38	46.64	58.60
1000	10	0.2	12	12	3	2.1	10	12	0.2	1.56	30.72	46.38	61.65
1000	10	0.2	12	12	3	2.2	10	12	0.2	1.54	29.41	44.47	63.73
1000	10	0.2	12	12	3	2.3	10	12	0.2	1.51	27.89	41.35	66.53
1000	10	0.2	12	12	3	2	10.5	12	0.2	1.57	34.31	47.36	56.02
1000	10	0.2	12	12	3	2	11.0	12	0.2	1.61	34.14	50.14	53.55
1000	10	0.2	12	12	3	2	11.5	12	0.2	1.61	35.01	52.95	50.78
1000	10	0.2	12	12	3	2	10	12.6	0.2	1.66	30.43	55.46	67.83
1000	10	0.2	12	12	3	2	10	13.2	0.2	1.75	27.89	66.15	76.44
1000	10	0.2	12	12	3	2	10	13.8	0.2	1.83	25.57	73.71	82.67
1000	10	0.2	12	12	3	2	10	12	0.21	1.50	34.51	41.79	47.19
1000	10	0.2	12	12	3	2	10	12	0.22	1.45	35.66	38.51	38.68
1000	10	0.2	12	12	3	2	10	12	0.23	1.41	37.21	35.71	31.31

From Table 3 it is observed that the deterioration parameter and replenishment parameters have a tremendous influence on the optimal values of the model.

When ordering cost A increases from 1000 to 1150, the optimal replenishment time t_1^* decreases from 1.57 to 1.52, the optimal selling price s^* increases from 33.26 to 35.70, the optimal

ordering quantity Q^* decreases from 46.63 to 42.58, the total profit P^* decreases from 58.80 to 44.99. As the cost per unit 'C' increases from 10 to 11.5, the optimal replenishment time t_1^* decreases from 1.57 to 1.54, the optimal selling price s^* increases from 33.26 to 34.85, the optimal ordering quantity Q^* decreases from 46.63 to 43.99, the total profit P^* increases from 44.49 to 52.71. When the holding cost 'h' increases from 0.2 to 0.23, the optimal replenishment time t_1^* increases from 1.57 to 1.59 and the total profit P^* increases from 58.80 to 59.14, the optimal selling price s^* decreases from 33.26 to 32.26, the optimal ordering quantity Q^* increases from 46.63 to 48.88.

As the replenishment ' α ' increases from 12 to 13.6, the optimal replenishment time t_1^* decreases from 1.57 to 1.49, the optimal selling price s^* increases from 33.26 to 33.74, the optimal ordering quantity Q^* decreases from 46.63 to 46.15, the total profit P^* decreases from 58.80 to 58.42. Another replenishment parameter ' β ' increases from 3 to 3.45, the optimal replenishment time t_1^* decreases from 1.57 to 1.48, the optimal selling price s^* increases from 33.26 to 33.38, the optimal ordering quantity Q^* increases from 46.63 to 46.64, the total profit P^* decreases from 58.80 to 58.60.

As the deteriorating parameter ' γ ' varies from 2 to 2.3, the optimal replenishment time t_1^* decreases from 1.57 to 1.51, the optimal selling price s^* decreases from 33.26 to 27.89, the optimal ordering quantity Q^* decreases from 46.63 to 41.35, the total profit P^* increases from 58.80 to 66.53. Another deteriorating parameter ' α ' varies from 10 to 11.5 the optimal replenishment time t_1^* increases from 1.57 to 1.61, the optimal selling price s^* increases from 33.26 to 35.01, the optimal ordering quantity Q^* increases from 46.63 to 52.95, the total profit P^* increases from 58.80 to 50.78.

As the demand parameter ' η ' increases from 12.6 to 13.8, the optimal replenishment time t_1^* increases from 1.57 to 1.83, the optimal selling price s^* decreases from 33.26 to 25.57, the optimal ordering quantity Q^* increases from 46.63 to 73.71, the total profit P^* increases from 58.80 to 82.67. Another demand parameter ' θ ' increases from 0.2 to 0.23 the optimal replenishment time t_1^* decreases from 1.57 to 1.41, the optimal selling price s^* increases from 33.26 to 37.21, the optimal ordering quantity Q^* decreases from 46.63 to 35.71, the total profit P^* decreases from 58.80 to 31.31.

10. SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS OF THE MODEL

The sensitivity analysis is carried to explore the effect of changes in model parameters and costs on the optimal policies, by varying each parameter (-15%, -10%, -5%, 0%, 5%, 10%, 15%) at a time for the model under study. The results are presented in Table 4. The relationship between the parameters and the optimal values of the replenishment schedule is shown in Figure 4.

It is observed that the costs are having significant influence on the optimal replenishment quantity and replenishment schedules. As the ordering cost A decreases, the optimal replenishment time t_1^* , the optimal ordering quantity Q^* and total profit P^* are increasing and the optimal selling price s^* decreases. As the ordering cost A increases, the optimal replenishment time t_1^* , the optimal ordering quantity Q^* and optimal profit P^* are decreasing, the optimal selling price s^* increases. When the cost per unit C decreases, the optimal replenishment time t_1^* , the optimal value of ordering quantity Q^* and total profit P^* are increasing, the optimal selling

price s^* decreases. When the cost per unit C increases, the optimal replenishment time t_1^* , the optimal ordering quantity Q^* and total profit P^* are decreasing, the optimal selling price s^* increases. When the holding cost 'h' decreases, the optimal replenishment time t_1^* , the optimal ordering quantity Q^* are increasing and total profit P^* , the optimal selling price s^* are decreasing, when the holding cost 'h' increases, the optimal replenishment time t_1^* , the optimal ordering quantity Q^* and total profit P^* are increasing and the optimal selling price s^* decreases.

As the replenishment parameter ' α ' decreases, the optimal values of t_1^* and P^* are increasing, the optimal ordering quantity Q^* and the optimal selling price s^* are decreasing. As replenishment parameter ' α ' increases, the optimal replenishment time t_1^* , the optimal ordering quantity Q^* and total profit P^* are decreasing, the optimal selling price s^* increases. As another replenishment parameter ' β ' decreases, the optimal values of t_1^* and P^* are increasing, the optimal ordering quantity Q^* and the

optimal selling price s^* are decreasing. As the parameter β increases, the optimal values of t_1^* and P^* are decreasing, the optimal ordering quantity Q^* and the optimal selling price s^* are increasing.

As deteriorating parameter γ decreases, the optimal replenishment time t_1^* , the optimal ordering quantity Q^* , the optimal selling price s^* are increasing and total profit P^* decreases. As the deteriorating parameter γ increases, the optimal replenishment time t_1^* , the optimal ordering quantity Q^* , the optimal selling price s^* are decreasing and total profit P^* increases. Another deteriorating parameter a decreases, the optimal replenishment time t_1^* , the optimal ordering quantity Q^* , the optimal selling price s^* are decreasing and total profit P^* increases. As the deteriorating parameter a increases, the optimal replenishment time t_1^* , the optimal ordering quantity Q^* , the optimal selling price s^* are increasing and total profit P^* decreases.

As the demand parameter η decreases, the optimal replenishment time t_1^* , the optimal ordering quantity Q^* and total profit P^* are decreasing, the optimal selling price s^* increases. As the parameter η increases, the optimal values of t_1^* and P^* are increasing, the optimal ordering quantity Q^* and the optimal selling price s^* are decreasing. Another demand parameter θ decreases, the optimal values of t_1^* , Q^* , P^* are increasing and the optimal selling price s^* decreases. When the parameter θ increases, the optimal values of t_1^* , Q^* , P^* are decreasing and the optimal selling price s^* increases.

Table 4

Sensitivity analysis of the model - without shortages

Variation Parameters	optimal policies	Change in parameters						
		-15%	-10%	-5%	0%	5%	10%	15%
A	t_1^*	1.64	1.63	1.60	1.57	1.55	1.53	1.52
	s^*	28.94	29.92	31.59	33.26	34.03	34.99	35.70
	Q^*	53.74	52.14	49.39	46.63	45.36	43.76	42.58
	P^*	67.84	65.10	62.50	58.80	54.47	49.78	44.99
C	t_1^*	1.61	1.60	1.58	1.57	1.58	1.56	1.54
	s^*	30.98	31.57	32.51	33.26	33.43	33.53	34.85
	Q^*	50.39	49.42	47.87	46.63	46.34	46.19	43.99
	P^*	64.19	62.44	60.72	58.80	56.76	54.92	52.71
h	t_1^*	1.573	1.573	1.573	1.572	1.572	1.59	1.591
	s^*	33.19	33.21	33.23	33.26	33.21	32.27	32.26
	Q^*	46.74	46.71	46.68	46.63	46.58	48.26	48.88
	P^*	58.33	58.49	58.64	58.80	58.95	58.98	59.14
a	t_1^*	1.65	1.64	1.60	1.57	1.56	1.53	1.49
	s^*	32.09	32.23	32.93	33.26	33.35	33.72	33.74
	Q^*	46.51	48.06	47.06	46.63	46.43	46.19	46.15
	P^*	59.18	58.90	58.91	58.80	58.53	58.52	58.42
β	t_1^*	1.70	1.65	1.61	1.57	1.53	1.50	1.48
	s^*	33.08	33.15	33.21	33.26	33.30	33.34	33.38
	Q^*	46.63	46.63	46.63	46.63	46.63	46.63	46.64
	P^*	59.08	58.98	58.88	58.80	58.72	58.66	58.60
γ	t_1^*	1.62	1.63	1.61	1.57	1.56	1.54	1.51
	s^*	37.34	36.01	34.03	33.26	30.72	29.41	27.89
	Q^*	52.38	51.10	50.18	46.63	46.38	44.47	41.35
	P^*	43.24	48.11	54.30	58.80	61.65	63.73	66.53
a	t_1^*	1.54	1.55	1.56	1.57	1.59	1.61	1.64
	s^*	29.48	31.08	31.22	33.26	34.31	34.14	35.01
	Q^*	44.10	44.69	45.24	46.63	47.36	50.14	52.95
	P^*	65.06	63.60	60.88	58.80	56.02	53.55	50.78
η	t_1^*	1.32	1.39	1.48	1.57	1.66	1.75	1.83
	s^*	36.42	35.84	34.84	33.26	30.43	27.89	25.57
	Q^*	28.04	33.05	39.00	46.6	55.46	66.15	73.71
	P^*	21.23	33.99	46.11	58.80	67.83	76.44	82.67
θ	t_1^*	1.75	1.70	1.64	1.57	1.5	1.45	1.41
	s^*	27.76	28.64	30.87	33.26	34.51	35.6	37.21
	Q^*	64.44	58.90	53.10	46.63	41.79	38.51	35.71
	P^*	71.85	69.72	65.42	58.80	47.19	38.68	31.31

Fig 4: Relationship between optimal values and parameters without shortages.

11. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we developed and analyzed an inventory model with random production and Pareto rate of decay. Here is assumed that replenishment is a finite and follows two parameter Weibull distribution further is assumed that the deterioration is also random and follows generalized Pareto distribution, the Weibull rate of production includes increasing/decreasing/constant rates of production. The generalized rate of Pareto decay characterizes the delayed decay and includes Exponential and Uniform distributions as limiting cases. Using the differential calculus the instantaneous rate of deterioration and total profit rate function is obtained. The optimal pricing and ordering policies of the model are derived under unconstrained optimization. The sensitivity analysis of the model reveals that the optimal pricing and ordering policies of the model are influenced by the replenishment, distribution parameters and deterioration distribution parameters. The without shortages model is also analyzed as a limiting case. This model is useful for managers operating inventory control for taking optimal decisions by estimating the cost values from historical data. The proposed model is much used for analysing situation arising at places like Warehouses, food and chemical processing industries where the production is random and deterioration is catastrophes.

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